

The Influence of POV Trend as a Branding Image Content Creator on TikTok

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Abstract:- On TikTok, there is a POV content trend or point of view, which is a phrase in Indonesian. The POV trend in the TikTok app appears to be a mimic of what Jean Baudrillard refers to as reality. The POV trend has unconsciously drawn in an unreal simulation. The TikTok application is associated with a phenomena known as hyperreality. This study aims to answer the following research questions: How are TikTok content makers analyzing POV developments from the perspective of Jean Baudrillard? The reasons behind the trending POV-themed content were discovered using a qualitative descriptive study method and Jean Baudrillard's simulacra and hyperreality investigations, namely: (1) engaging the viewers' emotions; (2) the presence of special effects characteristics; and the TikTok algorithm. According to Jean Baudrillard, today's society lives in the guise of a fake reality influenced by technical sophistication, such as the TikTok application with all of its capabilities.

Keywords:- Trend POV, TikTok, Simulacra Dan Hyperreality, Baudrillard.

I. INTRODUCTION

The more advanced technology becomes, the more people utilize social media to find information and entertain themselves. To demonstrate society's existence, media becomes branding (Setijowati & Firdaus, 2021; Firdaus, Bramantio & Afdholy, 2023). Social media posts frequently become trending among social media users (Jain et al, 2021; Barnes, 2006; Herring and Kapidzic, 2015). TikTok is a popular social media platform among the general public. Scherr and Wang (2021); Yang and Ha (2021); Arkansyah et al. (2021). According to Wijaya and Mashud's (2020) TikTok is a Chinese social networking application and music platform that was released in September 2016.

TikTok app users can make movies ranging in length from 15 seconds to 5 minutes (Xu and Zhang, 2019; Yang et al., 2019; Dewi, 2021). It may make videos more entertaining by including elements such as special effects and background music. This then promotes Tik Tok users' ingenuity to become content makers. It's no surprise that numerous types of uploaded content have become a trend in the application. There is a POV or point of view content trend on TikTok, or the term in Indonesian is a point of view. The POV trend refers to the content's creator's point of view (Dian on Narration.tv on April 12, 2023).The audience

is supposed to understand the feelings or intentions that the creator wishes to convey through the content. The creator wants the audience to think of themselves as creators in this way.

One of the catalysts for the creation of emerging trends in society is the phenomena of consumerism society (Fatria & Christantyawati, 2018; Ridwan et al., 2018). Trends in social media are popular because they are simple to follow and spread swiftly in all circles (Adiarsi et.al, 2015). Tiktok is a popular social networking platform in Indonesia (Dewa and Safitri, 2021). According to Kompasdata (Galuh, 2023), the number of TikTok users in Indonesia was estimated to be 113 million in April 2023. During that time span, Indonesia became the world's second largest Tik Tok user. Then, according to data kataid.co.id (Annur, 2023) Tik Tok users reached 109.9 million in February 2023, up from roughly 13 million in April.

Fig. 1. Tik Tok User Data in Indonesia 2023

Source:

<https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2023/02/27/indonesia-sabet-position-kedua-As-negara-pengguna-tiktok-terbanyak-di-dunia-pada-awal-2023>.

Based on the statistics shown above, the graph depicts Indonesia's standing in relation to the United States. Trends on TikTok are something that is not only practiced but also consumed by the public; TikTok's influence, particularly in the formation of certain trends, is very broad given the vast number of TikTok users in Indonesia. (Fuaddah, Nurhaeni, & Rahmanto, 2022; Haryanto, 2022). Many public TikTok

trends have been carried out, including the Bold Glamor filter, Barbie, Aged, Lovely Dog, and Miley Cyrus filters. TikTok users frequently utilize a number of slang phrases. First and foremost, FYP, the #FYP hashtag, is used as a landing page. TikTok's algorithm will recommend to other users using FYP. Second, CEO, which stands for Chief Executive Editor, is typically assigned to individuals who are experts in a specific topic or field. Third, POV, or Point of View, is a word that is frequently used as a hashtag in videos to inform the audience that the video being watched is from the reader's point of view. In other words, the audience feels as though they are experiencing or witnessing the event depicted in the TikTok video. Pick Me Girl, Chuaks, Glow Up, and Flex/Flexing are other phrases that are commonly used in the TikTok app.

Previous research by Abidin (2021) concentrated on the internet and celebrities on TikTok, while Dias and Duarte (2022) explored teens in Portugal who use TikTok. The focus in this study is on Trend POV, which is related to the creator's branding image. Aside from that, it appears that the POV trend on the TikTok program is a simulation of reality, as Jean Baudrillard refers to it. Unknowingly, the POV trend has locked it in an unreal simulation. The TikTok application is associated with a phenomena known as hyperreality. Consumers who operate as subjects in the realm of hyperreality are herded into the experience of hyperreality space with mixed experiences and the melting of reality into non-reality. This study seeks to formulate the following research questions using Jean Baudrillard's perspective: How are TikTok content makers analyzing POV developments from the perspective of Jean Baudrillard? This is intended to be able to grasp the causes for trending this POV material in the TikTok application from Jean Baudrillard's standpoint.

II. METHOD

The descriptive qualitative research method was utilized in this study, and the results are presented in written form in the form of words, phrases, paragraphs, and even paragraphs. The TikTok context in the shape of a POV trend is the subject of this piece. The data source used in this study is primary data taken directly from the research object, namely the POV trend obtained on the TikTok application on the accounts @clayre_prb, @bisrillhafii, @feliidebbii, @sprakori_, and @englishwithk_.

The five TikTok accounts were selected because they frequently utilise POV trends in their TikTok posts. The followers of the five TikTok accounts total over 1,000, and they are active in uploading POV trends. Secondary data is also gathered from a variety of scientific literature such as journals, essays, and even theses whose research focus is similar to the research being researched in this study.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

➤ Identity and Pleasure and on TikTok

Trend POV refers to the creator's perspective on the content (McGorry, 2022). It is believed that this content would be able to help the viewers understand the creator's sentiments or objectives. Creators want the audience to see themselves as creators in this way (McGorry, 2022). According to Jean Baudrillard, today's society is a consumerist society (Baudrillard, 1998). Consumerist society tends to ignore use value and prioritize exchange value (Baudrillard, 1998). Consumerist society is vital to lifestyle through expressing oneself in various elements of daily life. This is the same as pretending to be someone else. As seen in the following two images.

Image 2.

Upload of the TikTok account @clayre_prb

Image 3.

Upload of the TikTok account @bisrillhafii

The two uploads appear normal at first glance because they only include one individual talking to himself. Because it is used in the TikTok application, the POV trend alters the upload scenario. Uploads from the TikTok accounts @claire_prb and @bisrillahafii can be described as a consumer society playing with identity by portraying two persons with opposing viewpoints. Figure 2 depicts a conversation between two individuals on the @clayre_prb account. The POV used reveals the identity of the content provider, ensuring that the TikTok audience sees and enjoys the content.

Aside from that, content providers can have their material become FYP or trending on TikTok, expanding their audience reach. The content creator's identity demonstrates that he can develop conversational material even when he is alone. The method in the above upload is accomplished by shifting the camera's point of view as if there were two sides. This identity is enjoyed by content creators in order to demonstrate their existence, as well as by the audience as a result of the information communicated by content creators. The following is an excerpt from the above-pictured conversation.

"From your point of view, when did you find out about your boyfriend from your friends?" Friend: Hey, how's your relationship going?

Me: It's nothing, what's the problem?

Friend: I observed your boy walking with a girl the other day.

Me: Oiya... before you know it, I know it. I already have proof here. Friend: Woooooop

(TikTok account @clayre_prb upload)

The prominence of messages mocked by content creators is one of the shifts that are currently taking place in a consumerist society. Based on the discussion above, the premise is that it can invite the audience to engage and involve their sentiments if they experience a similar occurrence. The audience is required to remain calm in the face of unexpected issues. Figure 2 depicts a similar point of view trend. Figure 2's remark indicates that the creator wishes to express to the female audience that if an occurrence occurs in which a guy takes advantage of it, it is advisable to depart and forget about the man for wasting his time.

Nonetheless, these two uploads appear unreal because the audience has not actually experienced them; however, the creators are attempting to make the audience feel as though this incident occurred in the audience's real life. That is how simulacra and hyperreality research works (Baudrillard, 1998). The viewer is invited to feel as if they are experiencing events that they may not actually be experiencing through POV content, and then invited to feel the situation created by the content provider.

Picture 4. Upload the TikTok account @feliidebbii

Picture 5.

Upload the TikTok account @sptrakori_

Picture 6.

Upload the TikTok account @englishwithk_

The usage of identity in making POV material is not confined to one gender; content creators can be male or female even if their original gender is different. For the purpose of animating the role and displaying the TikTok account's branding picture in order to entice the audience to watch the material that is presented. Finally, makers construct a universe that requires identity and pleasure for society.

➤ *Special Effects as Simulacra*

The TikTok application, as is generally known, has a special effect option that, when employed, may transform a person into a different version of themselves. These special effects can transform the contour or expression of a person's

face, making them look lovely, handsome, youthful, or old. The following two images demonstrate this. 'The universe and all of us,' argues Baudrillard, 'have entered live into simulation' (Baudrillard, 1998). This argument that we have entered an era of 'simulation' is one of Baudrillard's most renowned and contentious ideas. His concept of the 'simulacrum' has since attracted a great deal of critical and popular attention, becoming a widely used concept, widely accepted by many academics and students as an invaluable tool of cultural and media analysis; a catch-all term with cutting-edge kudos to be applied to all manifestations of our image-society, as well as a fashionable trope for broadsheet 'media' and 'culture' (Merrin, 2001).

Picture 6.

Upload the TikTok account @yochands

Picture 7.

Upload the TikTok account @idulbukidoel

The two images above are from video uploads by the TikTok accounts @yochands and @idulbukidoel. Both of these accounts use special effects to make the creators appear different from the original. TikTok creator @yochands employs a particular effect that can change the form of his face (Wang et al, 2023; Yang et al, 2020; Warburton, 2022). This is done to make it appear as if the content is being played by two different people. however only one person appears in the video (Wang et al, 2022). The same can be said for the author of @idulbukidoel, who

employs a special effect to modify his facial expression to melancholy to match the theme of his content, which is about crying.

According to the special effects function, the TikTok application presents an existence that exceeds one's essence (Wijaya and Mashud, 2020: 180). The employment of the special effects function allows for the coexistence of fake imaginations and authenticity. This is due to the fact that special effects bring forth the intended reality. Naturally,

reality is more beautiful than reality. Humans are constantly bombarded with pseudo and artificial visuals via the TikTok application's special effects feature, therefore it is not uncommon for someone to present a reality that is diametrically opposed to their own. The reality created by the maker is, of course, significant, as Baudrillard emphasizes Simulacra.

➤ *Hyperreality in Algoritma TikTok*

TikTok content with a POV trend is something to keep an eye on the platform. When the viewer views the content and watches it all the way through, the TikTok algorithm recognizes it as an excellent video. The TikTok homepage will thereafter continue to offer similar information. Furthermore, the audience consumes this stuff. According to Baudrillard (1998), consumption is very crucial in human life. In this situation, it is referred to as a consumerist society.

TikTok has an algorithm that detects human desires based on the user's most recent upload, most recent search, and most recent search. The TikTok algorithm will offer more identical videos, as if it were displaying "our" tastes as consumers. Similar appearances frequently cause the audience and artists to enjoy each other's individual joys. Creators created hyperality to create a comfy environment for the viewers.

IV. CONCLUSION

As Jean Baudrillard describes it, the POV trend in TikTok is a simulation of reality. The participation of viewers' feelings, the special effects function, and the TikTok algorithm were subsequently identified as three factors for the trending content. According to Jean Baudrillard, today's society lives in the guise of a fake reality influenced by technical sophistication, such as the TikTok application with all of its capabilities. The options offered on the TikTok app encourage creators to be more creative and imaginative when creating such scenarios for their work. The researcher recognizes that this research is far from flawless, thus it is hoped that in future research, comparable things can be discussed, analyzed, and formulated more extensively, particularly by focusing on simulacra and hyperreality studies on social media TikTok.

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